

TOPIC: PHYSICAL CULTURE AND SPORTS**Akmal Tajiddinovich Khalikov**

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ANNOTATION*The article describes the importance of physical education in human life*

Key words: *physical education, human, life, being healthy, activity, running, exercise*

Physical culture is a part of general human culture, a sphere of social activity aimed at strengthening human health and developing physical abilities. The main indicators of the state of physical culture in the society: people's health and physical fitness, the degree to which physical culture is implemented in the field of upbringing and education, in life, achievements in sports, etc. Physical culture includes folk games, physical exercises, sports and forms of tourism that require active movement. Physical culture was formed and developed in connection with such sciences as medicine, ecology, pedagogy, psychology. It has a direct impact on the development of society, people's effective work, the development of mental abilities, moral purification, and the physical condition of future generations.

Physical education, physical education is an integral part of general education aimed at strengthening health and harmonious development of the human body. It is one of the indicators indicating the state of physical culture in society. The main means of physical education: physical training, physical training, work and life hygiene. Physical education is combined with intellectual, moral, work and aesthetic education.

Special attention has been paid to physical education since the elementary period. Initially, it represented various rituals, which existed in the form of physical exercises,

various games, labor processes, hunting, competitions and trials similar to military operations. Later, training young people in swordsmanship, horse riding, archery, and one-on-one combat became one of the main tasks of the society. During the renaissance, attention to physical education became even stronger. Humanists tried to include physical education in the curriculum. In medieval Europe, physical education was considered as an important part of family education and pedagogical process in school. J. J. Rousseau in his pedagogical treatise called "Emile, or About Education" emphasized the importance of J. t. in mental development and labor education of children. In the 18th century, mainly under the influence of Rousseau's ideas, the "schools of humanity and good behavior" - philanthropists, which appeared in Germany, led to the improvement of the forms and methods of physical education. Gymnastics takes a strong place in the school curriculum. At the end of the 19th century and the beginning of the 20th century, France, Great Britain, etc. National systems of physical education were formed in the countries.

In Uzbekistan, physical education has long been regarded as the main means of strengthening health. Mahmud Koshgari's work "Devonu Lugotit Turk" contains information about more than 100 folk games. "Alpomish" Uzbek folk heroic epic, "Farkhod va Shirin" by Alisher Navoi, "Badoye ul-vaqaye" ("Rare events" by Zayniddin Vasifi), "Boburnoma" by Babur, etc. examples are told.

By the years of independence in Uzbekistan, physical education and sports have risen to the level of state policy. In 1992 (and in 2000 in a new version) the adoption of the Law "On Physical Education and Sports", in 1993 the development of the Healthy Generation State Program, the Cabinet of Ministers on the Development of Special Types of Sports, and finally in 1999 "Physical Education and Sports in Uzbekistan" The decision "On measures for further development of sports" created the legal basis of physical education.

Wide-ranging system of physical education: family-preschool period (from infancy to kindergarten age), school age, secondary special and higher education period, and adult (male and female) physical education. In Uzbekistan, physical

education in secondary schools is considered a pedagogical process and is carried out through physical education classes and training in sports sections. 2 hours a week physical education classes have been introduced in grades 1-9 according to the "State Education Standard of Physical Education for General Secondary Schools". Special tests were developed in 1999 in order to popularize physical education among students and strengthen their health. "Alpomish" and "Barchinoy" badges of 3 levels were established for those who successfully passed these tests. 1,588,298 students successfully passed these tests (2002). Also, public competitions "Umid nihollar" for schoolchildren, "Barkamol Avlod" for lyceum-college students, and "Universiade" for university students were held every 2 years. "Alpomish Games" festival and "Tomaris Games" are held every 2nd year in terms of folk games and mass sports.

The scientific and practical foundations of physical education and specialists in this field are trained at the State Institute of Physical Education of Uzbekistan, faculties and departments of higher educational institutions. In the republic, 6 schools of Olympic substitutes, 8 schools of higher sports skills and 369 schools for children and teenagers also provide physical education lessons to students. Sports societies such as "Yoshlik" volunteer sports organization, "Vatanparvar" defense support organization, and "Dinamo" sports club serve to attract different layers of the population to physical training.

The modern broad concept of "physical education" means an organic component of general education - an educational, pedagogical process aimed at mastering the personal values of physical culture by an individual. In other words, the purpose of physical education is the formation of a person's physical culture, that is, the aspect of human general culture that helps to realize biological and spiritual potential. Physical education, whether we realize it or not, begins from the first days after the birth of a new person.

Pyotr Franzevich Lesgaft (1837-1909), a Russian teacher, anatomist and doctor in Russia, is the founder of the scientific system of physical education (actually - education), which harmoniously supports the mental development and moral education

of a young person. "Courses of Physical Education Teachers and Leaders" created by him in 1896 was the first higher educational institution for training specialists in physical education in Russia and became the prototype of the modern St. Petersburg Academy of Physical Education named after P.F. Lesgaft . . Graduates of the academy receive higher physical education and become specialists in various fields of physical culture, including the field of physical education, that is, the development of physical culture values by people. In relation to working in higher educational institutions, such a specialist is called a physical culture teacher or a teacher of the physical education department. The terms "physical education" should be distinguished from vocational training in special educational institutions and "physical education" in its original (according to P.F.Lesgaft) meaning of physical education. In English, the term "physical education" can be used in both senses. It should also be remembered that the English term "en:physical culture" is not used abroad in the sense of our broad understanding of "physical culture". There, depending on the specific direction of physical activity, the words "en: sport", "uz: physical training", "uz: physical training", "uz: fitness" etc. are used. together. , moral, aesthetic and work education ensures comprehensive development of the individual. In addition, these aspects of the general educational process are manifested in the process of physical education organized accordingly.

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